

THEORETICAL BASIS OF TEACHING ENGLISH COLLOCATIONS TO THE INTERMEDIATE LEVEL STUDENTS**Rahimli Aynura Huseynkhan,***Teacher,***Nasirova Hadiya Firudin,***Teacher,***Gulalyeva Narmina Namig***Teacher,**College of Construction under AzMIU, Azerbaijan***Abstract**

In order to more effectively implement the teaching of free word combinations, the development of a system that leads to the formation of a program of the mechanism of combining words in students is an important step towards ensuring the fluency of their speech. In order to speak correctly in any foreign language, it is necessary not only to pronounce words correctly or build a sentence grammatically correctly, but also to be able to choose the right word in a foreign language and correctly combine that word with other words. The ways to implement these issues are described in detail in the work. The main types of work for the formation of speech skills are conditional-speech, conditional-communicative works. These works imitate communication. Also, according to the accepted classification, there are types of speech and non-speech works. These works are works that imitate this or that type of speech activity in educational conditions, on the basis of specially organized language materials, taking into account the characteristics of the type of speech activity and the difficulties that arise in the process of assimilating speech materials by students. They can be contextual and situational.

Keywords: speech, exercises, communication, students

The main essence of speech exercises is to create conditions for using them as a means of partially natural communication in a foreign language. As mentioned, the greatest difficulties for students learning a foreign language are caused by verb phrases. It is for this reason that it was considered appropriate to organize the prepared training model on the basis of verb phrases. It should be noted that the main place in language faculties is given to the reproductive and productive stages. The exercises were developed at each stage taking into account the students' native, i.e. Azerbaijani, language, and ensured the creation of appropriate conditions to prevent the negative impact of this native language. The purpose of the first stage is to present word phrases to students in a comparative manner with their native language. It is at this stage that the necessary conditions should be created for the formation of lexical speech habits and speech-oriented language and conditional-speech tasks should be used. Despite the importance of conditional-speech tasks for the development of speech skills and habits, the implementation of a certain amount of language tasks creates the basis for the conscious implementation of subsequent speech tasks.

At the reproductive stage, conditional-speech, situational-variant tasks are performed. Here, the foundation is laid for students' ability to use word combinations in various conditions: imagined, using text materials; visually presented; based on the context of speech; within a certain topic; in situations.

At the productive stage, creative tasks are performed. Here, the word combinations to be mastered are used in the composition of situations, dialogues, stories; creative use of mastered word combinations is intended when performing tasks that serve to develop critical thinking in students.

Unlike ordinary groups, in addition to textbooks and teaching aids used in experimental groups, additional materials were also used. A new teaching system was selected for mastering free word combinations in English, and developed methodological work methods were applied.

Special tasks and sentence models on the technique of distinguishing free word combinations from fixed word combinations, as well as phraseological combinations, were included in the materials of the educational experiment. At this time, the adoption of word combination variability as a teaching unit ensured their mastery on the basis of communicative blocks. Thanks to the expansion of the communicative block, the options for the development of free word combinations increased, the mechanism of linking words in sentences was formed, and the approximate foundations of this activity were formed in students. At this stage, one of the main tasks of the study was to familiarize students with lexical units and free word combinations that carry the main meaning, and to create the ability to use words correctly in word combinations.

In this process, by drawing students' attention to the fact that there are certain differences between words that are considered equivalent in the two languages, it was possible to prevent the automatic transfer of the combinatorics mechanism mastered in the Azerbaijani language to English to a certain extent and reduce the number of errors.

Of course, the program that students completed regarding the receptive type of activity cannot reflect the complete mastery of free word combinations in English. The applied practical work methods are aimed only at creating approximate bases of activity, understanding concepts, establishing relationships between concepts, creating combinations with the proposed

words, filling in the missing word combinations, etc. served to complete and translate sentences. The use of mastered word combinations in the composition of certain situations and dialogues has also become an integral part of the work done.

The study showed that the language exercises consciously performed by lower-year students create a basis for the mastery of the learned English language as a means of communication. In this regard, in order to implement the communicative goal of teaching, instilling in students the ability to communicate in the foreign language they have learned constitutes a methodological model of teaching.

Based on the ideas explained, the exercises in the experimental groups were carried out on the basis of a system of communicative tasks. Conditional speech and real-speech tasks were used more often. The task of forming creative speech based on the read or listened text, text fragments, and short stories was performed. In this process, the development of the ability to correctly use free word combinations in place and in the structure of mastered blocks and the strategy of improving oral speech in the process of discussing texts and narrating requirements were taken as the basis.

We were able to summarize the results of the conducted research as follows:

In order to realize the communicative goal of teaching foreign languages in higher specialized schools, creative combination of lexical units and word combinations in foreign languages and their correct use in the process of written and oral speech are among the important problems in language learning practice.

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